

MAJIS Hyperspectral Observations of the Moon During the JUICE Earth–Moon Gravity Assist: Mineralogical and Thermal Analysis. F. Zambon¹, F. Tosi¹, F. Altieri¹, M. C. De Sanctis¹, S. Le Mouélic², G. Piccioni¹, F. Poulet³, Y. Langevin³, C. Royer³, F. Colaiuta^{1,4}, O. Karatekin⁵, A. Mura¹, and C. Carli¹ (francesca.zambon@inaf.it), ¹INAF-Istituto di Astrofisica e Planetologia Spaziali, via del Fosso del Cavaliere 100, 00133 Rome (Italy), ²LPG, UMR-CNRS 6112, Nantes Université, 44322 Nantes Cedex, France, ³Institut d’Astrophysique Spatiale, CNRS-Université Paris-Saclay, Orsay 91400, France, ⁴University of Rome “La Sapienza”, Department of Physics, Rome, Italy, ⁵Royal Belgian Institute for Space Aeronomy, 1180 Brussels, Belgium

Introduction: The Jupiter Icy Moons Explorer (JUICE) mission hosts the Moons and Jupiter Imaging Spectrometer (MAJIS), a visible–infrared hyperspectral imaging spectrometer (0.49–5.56 μm) designed to characterize the surface composition and physical properties of the Jovian icy satellites [1,2]. During the Earth–Moon gravity assist on 19 August 2024, MAJIS acquired hyperspectral observations of the lunar nearside, providing both an in-flight validation opportunity and the first new lunar hyperspectral dataset since Chandrayaan-1/M³, Cassini/VIMS, and Chandrayaan-2/IIRS.

The Moon constitutes an ideal calibration and science testbed due to its well-constrained mineralogical diversity and extensive legacy datasets. MAJIS acquired data from part of Mare Tranquillitatis and Mare Fecunditatis, which represent compositionally distinct regions, showing differences in FeO and TiO₂ content and basaltic evolution [3, 4]. Their contrasting pyroxene chemistries, combined with space weathering effects modify spectral properties of the lunar surface [5], offering a stringent benchmark for assessing MAJIS mineralogical retrieval capability [6].

In addition to compositional validation, the coexistence of reflected sunlight and thermal emission within the MAJIS spectral range provides a controlled environment for testing near-infrared thermal correction and retrieval approaches [7]. Although instantaneous observations do not constrain intrinsic thermophysical properties, they enable cross-validation of temperature and thermal removal strategies critical for future investigations of icy satellite surfaces [7].

Digital Formats: MAJIS acquired four hyperspectral cubes (C1–C4) covering an equatorial area between $\sim 21^\circ\text{E}$ and 61°E longitude and -11° to $+6^\circ$ latitude, encompassing Mare Tranquillitatis, Mare Fecunditatis, and adjacent highlands. Owing to illumination constraints (phase angle $\sim 90^\circ$), the present analysis focuses primarily on cubes C3 and C4 (incidence angles $< 60^\circ$), with supplementary analysis of C2. Data were processed from calibrated radiance to radiance factor (I/F), including saturation filtering, straylight correction below $\sim 1.3 \mu\text{m}$ [8, 9], thermal emission removal, and spectral smoothing [6]. Because high phase angles precluded the application of standard photometric corrections (e.g., Lommel–Seeliger [10, 11]), both I/F spectra and

ratioed spectra were analyzed. Spectral parameters derived include 1- and 2- μm pyroxene absorption band depths, band centers, and visible–near-infrared spectral slopes. Mineralogical interpretations were contextualized through comparison with legacy datasets from Clementine, M³, Kaguya/MI, LOLA, and LROC-WAC.

To ensure robust separation of reflected and emitted components, three independent thermal retrieval approaches were applied to the same dataset: (1) a Bayesian nonlinear inversion constrained by radiative transfer [7], retrieving temperature and emissivity simultaneously; (2) an empirical correction based on laboratory-derived lunar soil relationships [12]; and (3) a roughness-informed thermal model accounting for sub-pixel shadowing, self-heating, and anisothermality [13]. Cross-comparison of these methods provided quantitative assessment of uncertainties affecting spectral parameters in the 2.6–5.4 μm range.

Results: MAJIS spectra display prominent absorption features near ~ 1 and $\sim 2 \mu\text{m}$, diagnostic of Fe²⁺ electronic transitions in pyroxenes [14, 15], confirming the mafic nature of mare basalts. The deepest band depths occur within Mare Tranquillitatis and Mare Fecunditatis, particularly in fresh impact craters such as Maskelyne G (Figure 1, green spectrum) and Messier/Messier A, where excavation of less-weathered material enhances spectral contrast.

Figure 1: Panel a) illustrates the regions of interest selected within cube C4. Panel b) displays the corresponding mean spectra of the regions shown in panel a).

In Mare Tranquillitatis (cube C4), systematic shifts in the 2- μm band center indicate an increasing contribution of high-Ca clinopyroxene toward basin interiors, while localized crater materials exhibit signatures compatible with pigeonite-rich assemblages [6]. Mare Fecunditatis (cube C3) shows comparatively homogeneous band center distributions but clear spectral distinctions between

mature regolith and fresh ejecta. Highland terrains exhibit higher reflectance, weaker mafic absorptions, and reddened slopes consistent with feldspathic compositions and space weathering processes [5]. Combined spectral parameter and RGB composite maps robustly discriminate mare basalts, highland units, and fresh crater ejecta (Figure 2), in strong agreement with M³-derived products [3, 4], thereby validating MAJIS calibration and spectral performance.

Figure 2: RGB composite image derived from MAJIS cubes C2, C3, and C4. The red channel encodes the spectral slope calculated between 0.55 and 2.60 μm , the green channel represents the depth of the 2- μm absorption band, and the blue channel shows the depth of the 1- μm absorption band.

Thermal-emission-corrected spectra beyond 2.6 μm reveal potential broad absorptions, including a recurrent feature near $\sim 4.8 \mu\text{m}$ [6]. While possibly linked to mafic mineral components, residual uncertainties related to thermal removal and detector saturation above 4 μm warrant further investigation.

The intercomparison of thermal retrieval methods demonstrates consistent first-order temperature trends with solar illumination and mutual agreement within uncertainties over well-illuminated terrains (Figure 3). Bayesian and roughness-aware approaches provide greater stability at high incidence angles and over rugged surfaces, whereas empirical corrections perform adequately under favorable conditions. Comparisons with Diviner radiometer measurements [16, 17] confirm overall consistency in retrieved temperatures and highlight the wavelength dependence of lunar emissivity when transitioning from mid- to near-infrared regimes.

Figure 3: Surface temperature derived through the Bayesian inversion approach for the four MAJIS lunar observations (C1–C4), overlaid on a lunar

optical mosaic to provide geographic context. The color scale represents the retrieved surface temperature (in K), whereas the grayscale background highlights the lunar surface morphology. The observed temperature variations mainly result from differences in solar illumination along the JUICE ground tracks.

Overall, the MAJIS lunar dataset establishes a robust mineralogical and thermally corrected spectral benchmark. The strong agreement with legacy missions confirms the instrument’s capability to resolve compositional variability, surface maturity, and pyroxene composition. These results validate MAJIS performance during cruise and provide critical methodological foundations for the compositional and thermophysical investigation of the Jovian icy satellites.

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